

INDIGOID VAT DYES OF THE ISATIN SERIES. PART IV. 3-INDOLE
-2'-(7'-METHYL) THIONAPHTHENE-INDIGOS

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3-Indole-2'-(7'-methyl)-thionaphthene-indigos, having various types of substituents in the indole part of the molecule, have been prepared. These dyestuffs have been compared with the corresponding compounds belonging to the 4', 5'- and 6'-methyl series. The study of the various indole-(methyl)-thionaphthene-indigos having a methyl group in every theoretically possible position of the thionaphthene nucleus is now made complete and a generalisation is made with regard to the colour and the chemical constitution of these vat colours of the isatin series, as far as one Me group is concerned.

It is also observed that this generalisation is applicable to a symmetrical dye, thioindigo and all its isomeric dimethyl derivatives. The possibilities of using a number of dyes of this indole-(methyl) thionaphthene-indigo series on a commercial basis has been suggested.

With a view to investigating into the relation between the colour and the chemical constitution of thioindigoid vat dyes of asymmetrical structure, 3-indole-2'-thionaphthene-indigo (I), commercially known as Thioindigo Scarlet (Bezdzik and Friedländer, *Monatsh*, 1908, **29**, 376; E.P., 17162/06) which is a typical example of a vat dye composed of two dissimilar nuclei, was chosen and the influence of one CH₃ group in 4', 5', and 6' position of the thionaphthene nucleus of this dye and its different kinds of substituted products was studied in Parts I, II and III of this series (Guha and Basu-Mallick, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **11**, 395; Guha, *ibid.*, 1937, **14**, 240; 1938, **15**, 501)

This paper now deals with the preparation and a study of the various properties of 3-indole-2'-(7'-methyl)thionaphthene-indigos obtained by the condensation of 7-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene, recently prepared by the author (Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16**, 221; 1943, **20**, 38) with 5-chloro-, 5-bromo-, 5:7-dibromo-, 5-bromo-7-nitro-, and 5:7-dinitroisatin respectively. The parent compound was previously described (Guha, *loc. cit.*). A detailed study in this series of compounds has been made by the author [2-(4-, 5-, 6-, 7-methyl) thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos, Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **10**, 682; 1936, **13**, 94; 1938, **15**, 23; 1943, **20**, 37].

These 7'-methyl dyes are dark red, violet-red and violet crystalline substances. They are all soluble in pyridine and nitrobenzene. The dibromo compound is insoluble in alcohol and the rest are sparingly soluble in the same solvent. The chloro, bromo, and dibromo-dye dissolve in cold concentrated sulphuric acid producing a light green solution in each case: the bromo-nitro; and the dinitro-substance produce a green solution when treated similarly. All of them behave similar to the isomeric 4', 5', and 6'-methyl compounds when heated above their melting points.

Their dyeing shades are uniformly developed on cotton from an alkaline hydrosulphite vat, the colour of which also resembles that which was found in the case of the corresponding

4', 5', and 6'-methyl substances. They have also imparted true shades on wool from a dilute sulphuric acid bath. As the dyes of this series possess a darkish tinge, their real depth of colour with respect to those of the isomeric 4', 5'- and 6'-methyl dyes could be only understood easily by examining them at first in xylene solution and finally confirming by taking the absorption spectra of some of them and calculating the absorption maxima (Table I) from the microphotograms of the spectra of the same (Figs. 1, 2). It is noticed that these dyes are lighter than those of the corresponding compounds of the 4', 5'- and 6'-methyl series.

This result also points to the conclusion that the presence of substituents e.g. Cl, Br, NO₂, etc., either alone or duplicated or combination of two different groups in the indole part of the dye, has no influence in altering the generalisation deduced before by the author taking only the parent compound of this series into consideration *i.e.* the depth of colour of all the isomeric indole-(methyl) thionaphthene-indigos, the detailed study of which was fully done, may now be arranged in the following order: 5-methyl dye > 4-methyl dye > 6-methyl dye > 7-methyl dye. The position of the depth of the colour of the parent dye is next to that of the 5-methyl dye (Table I).

Next the author in order to find out the depth of colour of thioindigo and all its isomeric dimethyl derivatives, which are important instances of vat dyes of symmetrical structure, and to compare their relationship with those of the vat dyes of symmetrical structure, the isomeric indole-(methyl)thionaphthene-indigos under discussion, studied the 4:4', 5:5'-6:6'-dimethyl-thioindigos (Fig. 4 and Table II, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 506). The 7:7'-dimethyl-thioindigo was also prepared and its properties examined (Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 39). Now its absorption spectrum was taken and the absorption curve drawn. It will appear that this curve (Fig. 3) also shows two maxima analogous to its isomeric substances. From the colour and the absorption maxima (Table II) it is found that the

FIG. 1

Curve 1 refers to 3-(5:7-dibromo) indole-2'-(7'-methyl)-thionaphthylene-indigo.

FIG. 2

Curve 1 refers to 3-(5:7-dinitro) indole-2'-(7'-methyl)-thionaphthylene-indigo.

7:7'-dimethylthioindigo is the lightest of all in this series. Therefore, it may be summarised that the depth of colour of thioindigo and all its isomeric dimethyl products stand in the same relationship as to those of the indole-thionaphthene-indigo and its isomeric methyl substituted dyes (Table I and II). That is, the same generalisation with regard to the colour and the constitution is applicable to both the classes of vat dyes studied here.

FIG. 3

Curve 1 refers to 7:7'-dimethyl-thioindigo.

of the dye in the alkaline hydrosulphite vat and enhances the affinity for cotton fibre.

The scarlet-red dye, 3-indole-2'-(5'-methyl) thionaphthene-indigo is brilliant, pleasant and deeper than 3-indole-2'-thionaphthene-indigo (Th^hindigo Scarlet R). The deep red dye, 3-(5:7-dibromo) indole-2'-(5'-methyl) thionaphthene is also deeper than 3-(5:7-dibromo) indole-2'-thionaphthene-indigo (Ciba Red G) (Table I). The dyeing shades of these two above mentioned dyestuffs, 3-(5-iodo)indole-2'-(5'-methyl) thionaphthene-indigo, 3-(5:7-dibromo) indole-2'-(6'-methyl)-thionaphthene-indigo, 3-(5-bromo-7-nitro) indole-2'-(4', 5', 6', 7'-methyl) thionaphthene-indigos and 3-(5:7-dinitro) indole-2'-thionaphthene-indigo together with all its isomeric methyl derivatives are very attractive. They may receive technical application soon on account of their depth of colour, beautiful characteristic shade and also fastness.

Finally, it may be stated that the author's attempt to establish a complete relationship between the colour and the chemical constitution of the various isomeric indole-(methyl) thionaphthene-indigos and of dimethylthioindigos has been amply realised. In the thioindigoid series, a complete generalisation of this type, as far as one substituent is concerned, has been deduced now for the first time.

The future line of work in this series will be to examine how far this generalisation is applicable to 3-indole-2'-thionaphthene-indigo having different types of substituents present in every theoretically possible position of the thionaphthene nucleus of the dye. Work in this direction is being undertaken.

TABLE I

T = Thionaphthene-indigo.

Compounds.	Absorption maxima.
3-(5:7-Dibromo) indole-2'-T	4915 Å
3-(5:7-Dibromo) indole-2'-(4'-Me) T	4910
3-(5:7-Dibromo) indole-2'-(5'-Me) T	4998
3-(5:7-Dibromo) indole-2'-(6'-Me) T	4897
3-(5:7-Dibromo) indole-2'-(7'-Me) T	4830
3-(5:7-Dinitro) indole-2'-T	4950
3-(5:7-Dinitro) indole-2'-(4'-Me) T	4945
3-(5:7-Dinitro) indole-2'-(5'-Me) T	5070
3-(5:7-Dinitro) indole-2'-(6'-Me) T	4927
3-(5:7-Dinitro) indole-2'-(7'-Me) T	4905

TABLE II

Compounds.	Absorption maxima.	
	Longer.	Shorter.
Thioindigo	5250 Å	5028 Å
4:4'-Dimethylthioindigo	5248	5025
5:5'-Dimethylthioindigo	5615	5296
6:6' Dimethylthioindigo	5295	4936
7:7'-Dimethylthioindigo	4940	4350

As the result of the syntheses of a large number and variety of isomeric indole-(methyl) thionaphthene-indigos (Parts I, II, III and IV), valuable dyestuffs of red, blood-red, scarlet-red, deep red, dark red reddish violet and violet shade have been obtained. They are characterised by their individual distinctive shade and according to choice the dyestuff may be selected for use. It is observed that the introduction of a halogen atom in the indole part of the dye gradually deepens the colour and the brightness is decreased: and that of NO₂ group further deepens the colour. Moreover, the presence of NO₂ group greatly increases the solubility of

EXPERIMENTAL

3-(5-Chloro) indole-2'-(7'-methyl)-thionaphthene-indigo.—This dye separated from the red-brown solution, obtained by dissolving 5-chloro-isatin (0.544 g.) and 7-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.492 g.) in 50 c.c. of boiling glacial acetic acid, on treatment with concentrated hydrochloric acid (3 c.c.) and heating for 20 minutes. The fine, small, stout, dark-red needles (0.827 g.) were collected, washed with acetic acid and hot water. It was crystallised from a mixture of nitrobenzene and xylene (1,3) in dark red needles melting above 300°. It is difficultly soluble in xylene and acetic acid, sparingly soluble in chloroform. It dyes cloth in dark red shade from an alkaline hydrosulphite vat and wool in the same colour from an acid bath. (Found : Cl, 10.58. $C_{17}H_{10}O_2N$ ClS requires Cl, 10.83 per cent).

3-(5-Bromo) indole-2'-(7'-methyl)-thionaphthene-indigo was similarly obtained as dark-red small needles from a boiling solution of 5-bromo-isatin (0.678 g.) and 7-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.492 g.) in glacial acetic acid (50 c.c.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (3.4 c.c.). The new product (1.003 g.) was crystallised from xylene in dark red needles melting above 295°. The solubility of this dye and its dyeing shade on cotton and on wool resemble those of the chloro compound. (Found : Br, 21.47. $C_{17}H_{10}O_2NBrS$ requires Br, 21.51 per cent).

3-(5:7-Dibromo) indole-2'-(7'-methyl)-thionaphthene-indigo was prepared by boiling a solution of 5:7-dibromo-isatin (0.61 g.) and 7-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.328 g.) in 65 c.c. of glacial acetic acid and 3 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid for 25 minutes. The dark red needle-shaped substance (0.7915 g.) was crystallised from nitrobenzene in soft wooly clusters of needles melting above 310°. It is soluble in xylene, sparingly soluble in acetic acid, insoluble in chloroform. It dyes cotton in deep red shade from an alkaline hydrosulphite vat and wool in blood-red shade from an acid bath. (Found : Br, 35.33. $C_{17}H_8O_2NBr_2S$ requires Br, 35.47 per cent).

3-(5-Bromo-7-nitro) indole-2'-(7'-methyl)-thionaphthene-indigo.—The solution of 5-bromo-7-nitro-isatin (0.813 g.) and 7-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.492 g.) in 70 c.c. of hot glacial acetic acid on treatment with 5 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid gave a lumpy mass of the condensed product in violet-red shining wooly needles. Glacial acetic acid (30 c.c.) was further added and the solution boiled for 20 minutes. The dye (1.128 g.) was crystallised from a mixture of xylene and nitrobenzene (4:1) in dark violet-red needles melting above 305°. It is moderately soluble in xylene, sparingly soluble in acetic acid and chloroform. It imparts a dark red shade to cloth from an alkaline hydrosulphite vat and a reddish violet shade to wool from an acid bath. (Found : Br, 18.82. $C_{17}H_8O_4N_2BrS$ requires Br, 19.18 per cent).

3-(5:7-Dinitro) indole-2'-(7'-methyl)thionaphthene-indigo was prepared by heating 5:7-dinitro-isatin (0.474 g.) and 7-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.328 g.) in 40 c.c. of glacial acetic acid and concentrated hydrochloric acid (3 c.c.) for 20 minutes. The violet crystalline precipitate (0.688 g.) was collected, washed with acetic acid and hot water. It was crystallised from pyridine in fine wooly needles not melting below 315°. It is sparingly soluble in xylene, acetic acid and chloroform. It dyes cloth in dark red shade from an alkaline hydrosulphite vat and wool in dark violet shade from an acid bath. (Found : S, 7.91. $C_{17}H_8O_6N_2S$ requires S, 8.35 per cent).

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